

Project Briefing Paper: Decision Tree & Neural Network model approach for finding the relationship between the gender and the London Minimum Wage (LMW)

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Abstract- Decision Tree is a method of non-parametric supervised learning method used for regression and classification. Neural Network approach is a method of modeling set of algorithms closely resembling a human brain and designed to recognize patterns. LMW; commonly known as the London Minimum Wage is a controversial area that presumably affecting the employees above 25 years old in London compared to the living cost in London. It has been an established fact that there are possible gaps between many numbers of social groups, everywhere in the world, where the minimum wage is defined in respective job markets. The possible tendency could be the employers; bargaining power in the job market against the demand of the applicant. This research is intended to determine if there are significant relationship between the gender and the disbursement of the LMW among the employers, which in return will provide an insight on possible damaging trends in the job market and tranquility of the employee lifestyle.

Index Terms- Decision Trees (DTs), Neural Network (NNET), Machine Learning (ML), London Minimum Wage (LMW)

I. INTRODUCTION

This report carefully presents the steps during the application of DTs and NNET on determining statistical relationship between two components on the provided dataset as depended and independent. To test this a real-life scenario of the effect of wages and gender is taken in LMW category in Grater London Area.

This is motivated by the endeavor of the Economic Fairness Policy maintained by the Greater London Authorities' Economic Fairness initiative, and its aim towards the population of London; to free them from discrimination, and to create a labor market that will encourage everyone to share job satisfaction. It is a fact that the increasing employee support and flexibility can lead to create a healthy society.

II. DATA UNDERSTANDING

Data Collection: The data set is received in the form of a XLSX file from the <https://data.london.gov.uk/> data repository, and the

data was imported to SAS Enterprise Miner, after creating a new Diagram as “employee-earning-below-llw”,

Data Description: The data set used in this contains the following variables,

Year	Sex	Working pattern	Number of employee jobs below the London Living Wage	Confidence Intervals (+/-) (95%) for number of employee jobs below the London Living Wage	Percentage of employee jobs below the London Living Wage	Confidence Intervals (+/-) (95%) for percentage of employee jobs below the London Living Wage
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The screenshot displays the SAS Enterprise Miner software interface. On the left, a project tree shows a diagram named 'employees-earning-below-llw'. The main workspace shows a 'File Import' dialog box with the following properties:

Property	Value
General	
Node ID	FIMPORT
Imported Data	...
Exported Data	...
Notes	...
Train	
Variables	...
Import File	E:\MBA\DataMining\temp...
Maximum Rows to Import	1000000
Maximum Columns to Import	10000
Delimiter	,
Name Row	Yes
Number of Rows to Skip	0
Guessing Rows	500
File Location	Local
File Type	xlsx
Advanced Advisor	No
Rerun	No
Score	
Role	Train
General	

III. DATA PREPARATION & EXPLORATION

Once the data set is loaded- inside that particular dataset the Variable “Sex” of the person has been targeted with the other attributes, assigning it as the Target Variable.

In the next step the node “StatExplore” was used to generate summary and association statistics of the dataset.

In the output sheet, it was checked if there are any missing values but recognized that there were none. This ruled out the necessity of the Impute note and enabled to proceed the Data Partitioning stage.

Once the data set is loaded- inside that particular dataset the Variable “Sex” of

Variable	Role	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Missing	Minimum	Median	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Number_of_employee_jobs_below_th	INPUT	278259.3	169234.5	135	0	76000	229000	871000	1.515472	2.537018
Percentage_of_employee_jobs_belo	INPUT	22.7237	14.66602	135	0	6.6	16.4	53.8	0.781497	-0.93755
VAR1	INPUT	10246.67	3162.75	135	0	4000	10000	19000	0.631891	0.315381
VAR2	INPUT	0.934813	0.669854	135	0	0.3	0.6	2.9	1.338834	0.848124

In the next stage using the data partitioning module, the data was portioned the data in to three categories in percentages as follows,

For Training	40%
For Validation	30%
For Testing	30%

This 40% of the data was used for training purpose, and 30% for validation and finally in the testing 30% of the data will be used.

IV. DATA MODELING & EVALUATION

After the data preparation was completed it is set to be run through two types of data models for testing. In order to do this, a new “Control Point” was inserted to the flow.

This will enable the process flow to be split in to two Models.

In the Output sheet the Neural networks applied various types of weights to determine the pattern inside the data set.

In the Iteration Plot it is seen that the Neural Network did not achieve the local optimum and no training iterations.

As per the Output document, under the Test Statistics the “Average Squared Error” the Decision Tree scored a lower error value performing slightly better than the Neural Network.

V. PLAN FOR DEPLOYMENT

Under this practical condition, it was noted that the Decision Tree model is more suitable for constant evaluation of the trend in the employees earning below the London Living Wage (LLW). However, the used dataset did not provide sufficient data for the iteration plot in the Neural network model, hence it is advisable to carry out further tests comparing the two models, perhaps using additional variables such as Job Type, Age, Education and Ethnicity.

Tools for Deployment:

It is recommended to use a simple web application like using a tool such as “Flask” (Khanna, 2018). The idea here is to create a web app in the form of HTML form where more details can be extracted in the mode of survey. With the Real-time data that is being extracted this will provide an opportunity to retrieve more time-bound updated data and additional information than it was done using the dataset that was used in this study.

C. Comparison between Decision Tree Model and Neural Network Model

In order to compare the results of the Decision Tree Model and the Neural Network Model, a “Model Comparison” module was connected in the end with both the model.

VI. CONCLUSION: THE BENEFITS & RISKS

The primary objective of this study was to determine the relevance of the “sex” of a person for being in the employees earning below the London Living Wage (LLW). The Primary party that requires this information is a Non-profit organization and more inclined on the social welfare, therefore it will be hard to determine a commercial value for this initiative, if it is to be implemented. Therefore, it may run in to risk of not returning the financial interest. Furthermore, the type of model on this subject is intended to provide more societal influences that may take longer time to effect and even longer time to effect as individuals. But however, this study model may answer key issues that may arise due to the London Living Wage (LLW),

The results of the Model Comparison were as follows using a Score Ranking Overlay on the Target variable “Sex”, Fit Statistics and Output sheet.

such as health and welfare, crime rates, immigration and emigration of the expatriates.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Data.london.gov.uk, 2020. Employees Earning Below, The London Living Wage (LLW) – London Datastore. [online] Data.london.gov.uk. Available at: <<https://data.london.gov.uk/dataset/earning-below-llw>> [Accessed 14 May 2020].
- [2] Khanna, R., 2018. Designing A Machine Learning Model & Deploying It Using Flask On Heroku. [online] Medium. Available at: <<https://towardsdatascience.com/designing-a-machine-learning-model-and-deploying-it-using-flask-on-heroku-9558ce6bde7b>> [Accessed 16 May 2020].